

Science clubs and scientific and technological fairs: encouraging girls in exact sciences, engineering and information technology

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Abstract

This work is the report of an educational experience carried out as part of the actions of the project “Encouraging Girls in Science, Engineering and Information Technology” (EM&CT), under development at the University of Caxias do Sul (UCS). Through various activities promoted by UCS with five elementary and high schools, located in the region covered by UCS, the project has, among its main objectives: to contribute significantly to scientific and technological development and innovation in the schools of the region, and to encourage participation and training of female students for careers in exact sciences, engineering and information technology. Among the central actions of the project are the creation of a Science and Astronomy club and the promotion of scientific and technological fairs in each one of the co-executing school. In 2019, students of the co-executing schools, in their Science and Astronomy Clubs, developed projects that were presented at the fairs held at their schools. Subsequently, these research projects were presented selected works were presented at the Scientific and Technological Fair of Serra Gaúcha (MOSTRASEG), held at UCS. The results obtained showed that, in the way activities were promoted, participation, with projects carried out by students, in the referred events is one of the possibilities to achieve the proposed objectives.

Keywords: Science and Astronomy Clubs; Scientific Fairs; Project-based Learning; University-K12-Community Integration

1 Introduction

Proposing teaching and learning methodologies that aim to arouse students' interest in science is a way to promote a taste for scientific and technological areas. It is possible to awaken the scientific curiosity of young people through new pedagogical environments in their school context, avoiding the reproduction of information from traditional classes, which more prepare students to do well in tests and less involve them in the process of learning and in the emotion of the discovery. Particularly, attracting girls to science has been also an apprehension for many researchers concerned with gender issues and the importance of female participation in science, technology engineering and mathematics (STEM) (Rasmussen & Hapnes, 1991; Anderson, 1994; NSF, 1998; Blickenstaff, 2005; Du & Kolmos, 2009; Tessari & Villas-Boas, 2013; Dasgupta & Stout, 2014; González-González et al, 2018; Sauer et al, 2020).

In Brazil, the process of insertion of women in scientific and technological careers occurred in the same proportions as in other countries of the world, however, during much of the twentieth century there was still a great prejudice related to women's aptitude or even to their intellectual abilities to pursue these careers (Tessari & Villas-Boas, 2013).

In this context, incentive programs and valorisation of female participation in STEM are presented as a solution through which this scenario may have possibilities to be reversed. In the last decade, the National Council for Research and Development (CNPq) has launched a considerable number of public calls aimed at supporting projects intended to stimulate the promotion of scientific fairs and the education of women for careers in Exact Sciences, Engineering and Information Technology in Brazil.

This paper reports, actions related to the creation of science clubs and scientific and technological fairs of a project approved in the last public call of CNPq, and that is underway at the University of Caxias do Sul, a community institution of higher education located in the southern region of Brazil. This project, called “Encouraging Girls in Science, Engineering and Information Technology” (EM&CT), is developed in partnership with five public elementary and high schools in the region of the university and is coordinated by a team of instructors that has been promoting for over ten years various activities to encourage young students in the

field of Exact Sciences and Engineering. The main objective of this study is to determine the progress achieved by the female students participating in the project, particularly with regard to science clubs and fairs, and to collaborate with these results for STEM education in Brazil and for engineering education at the level of basic education, awakening vocations and talents.

2 The Project EM&CT

All the actions of this project were proposed with the intention of valuing the school as a strategic and important space for the promotion of good pedagogical practices, to approximate the elementary and high schools and the university, to encourage female students from these schools to careers in Exact Sciences, Engineering and Information Technology, and to combat the dropout of female undergraduate students from the university, which occurs mainly in the early years, creating opportunities for them to act as scholarship holders for research and extension projects. Despite this project being conceived for girls, boys are also welcomed to participate in the activities.

Among the central actions of the project, we would like to highlight the creation of a Science and Astronomy club and the promotion of scientific and technological fairs in each one of the co-executing school.

The methodology of planning and carrying out the project actions involves the joint action of the participants of the university and the co-executing schools. This team, which comprises 13 faculty and five undergraduate students from the university, along with five teachers and 15 students from the co-executing schools, is responsible for carrying out activities at the Science and Astronomy club and to promote a scientific and technological fair in each co-executing school. These activities reach an estimated population of approximately 1,000 students from the co-executing schools.

In order to achieve the proposed objectives, the activities related to the Science and Astronomy club and to the scientific and technological fair were conceived considering active learning strategies and methods, in particular, project and problem based project (Savin-Baden & Howell-Major, 2004; Graaff & Kolmos, 2007; Bell, 2010; Villas-Boas et al., 2016; Merritt, 2017; Beier et al, 2019), in order to establish connections between the basic knowledge of the Exact and Natural Sciences and the practical applications to solve real problems of students' daily lives.

The activities, in this project, are intended to make knowledge accessible as it promotes the development of the autonomy of those involved in the process, as well as it seeks to promote the knowledge building and to promote interdisciplinary posture and practice.

3 Science Clubs

A science club is a pedagogical space for scientific studies in a perspective of building and producing knowledge, presenting strong integration with the community, and finding its participants involved in an atmosphere of cooperation and solidarity (Pires *et al.*, 2007). In this project, these clubs were designed to be created and managed at each co-executing school by the responsible teacher and fellow students of the project under the guidance of the coordinating team from the university. The activities carried out at each Science and Astronomy club take place during overtime and focus on studying, solving complex problems, developing projects and debates on topics involving science and technology. In this context, the club is the place where the "members" expose their ideas, their curiosities and seek to build knowledge, collaboratively, and using the scientific methodology. At the Science and Astronomy clubs, girls and boys developed questions, delineated a project, and were guided through research under their teacher's supervision. In project-based learning, the students' choice for what they want to research in their projects is the key element of this approach. Teachers supervise each step of the process and approve each project theme before the student starts to develop it. Students with similar research questions are advised to work cooperatively, thus nurturing 21st century collaboration and communication skills and honouring students' individual learning styles or preferences (Bell, 2010).

The Science and Astronomy Clubs are active in the co-executing schools of the EM&CT project and present the following history and current scenario:

- at Farroupilha school, the creation of the Science and Astronomy Club was encouraged by the EM&CT project team and is in its implementation phase, with the goal of fully integrating itself into the school's activities of 2020. In 2019, the school team, involved in the project, declared that it was touched by the others and started to carry out three projects, among which one of the projects managed to participate in the Scientific and Technological Fair of Serra Gaúcha (MOSTRASEG), an event to be described in section 4.2. We consider this an advance and merit of the EM&CT project, whose teacher representative of the school declared that they had never developed projects with scientific methodology.
- at Tancredo Neves school, the Science and Astronomy Club was created successfully in 2019 and as an EM&CT project activity. The school managed to implement several actions and projects, including organizing the school's own Scientific Fair and participating with a project in MOSTRASEG.
- at the Melvin Jones school, a space that served as a warehouse for scrap materials was revitalized. The scholarship holder teacher, together with the scholarship girls and other volunteer students, selected and labeled usable materials for use in the Science and Astronomy Club. Initially, in the new space, the workshops promoted by the EM&CT project were held, and shortly thereafter, work with projects, among which, ten participated in MOSTRASEG.
- at the Elisa Tramontina and João Pilati schools, the Science and Astronomy Clubs were already active, having been created before their participation in the EM&CT project.

During 2019, in addition to carrying out the projects under the guidance of teachers, the following workshops were held at the aforementioned Science and Astronomy Clubs: Astronomy; Preparation of alcoholic tincture, from fresh plants; Solid waste; Exploring smartphones; Information systems in digital media and Computational thinking and Robotics. These workshops were all promoted by the EM&CT project, and guided by UCS teachers to be applied to students from co-executing schools.

Figures 1 and 2 show images of students working in their Science and Astronomy Clubs.

Figure 1. Science Club at Melvin Jones School

Figure 2. Science Club at Elisa Tramontina School

4 Scientific and Technological Fairs

The scientific and technological fair, organized in each co-executing school of the EM&CT project, is an activity in which students present research projects developed throughout the year. The fair has among its main objectives (Barcelos, Jacobucci & Jacobucci, 2010): to awaken or develop a taste for research and experimentation; develop students' creativity and critical thinking; develop students' social habits and attitudes and a sense of responsibility; develop students' specific skills, interests and competences; in addition to integrating the community with the school.

To achieve these objectives, students are involved in carrying out projects, guided by teachers participating in the Continuing Education Course, promoted by the EM&CT project, in which one of the objectives is to promote skills in research methodology. The scientific and technological fair is organized and coordinated, in each co-executing school, by the scholarship holder teacher, assisted by students from the Science and Astronomy Clubs.

4.1 Scientific Fairs in the co-executing schools

The schools' scientific fairs, promoted considering the objectives already mentioned, intend to provide students with access to the scientific community, through research. Although the projects presented are not innovative, considering the social reality in which each of the schools is inserted, the incentive and support for carrying out research projects, throughout K-12, can be seen as a first step towards the formation of researchers at the basic level, who may become, in the future, researchers of fundamental questions for the progress of Science and Technology. As one of the results of the Science and Astronomy Clubs to be highlighted, entrepreneurship can already be observed in students in the final years of elementary school and, even more, in high school.

The development of scientific fairs in each of the schools is always a reason for great expectations and satisfaction on the part of all those involved (school community, students and teachers), as it is a time when all the projects, carried out and supervised in stages, are presented in their final version. During students' explanations, while presenting their work, one can perceive the commitment, the challenges faced and the evolution to reach the objectives that they set out to achieve. Indeed, each student also recognizes his own evolution and demonstrates its personal satisfaction. Research often creates a perspective for the future of young people who had no perspective at all, and also opens horizons and makes the student realize that she/he is capable of much more than she/he believes, much more than society imagines and all of this going through the paths and challenges that science presents her/him.

The scientific fair is the moment when it is possible to observe skills such as oral communication, student engagement and motivation. These skills are the result of the work developed with project-based learning. When attending a presentation, for which the student is responsible, it is evident her/his dedication and enthusiasm to publicize her/his work and her/his achievements with the project. It is also visible that the teacher's interaction and encouragement are fundamental for the student to recognize her/his full potential.

Created to be spaces for discussions on topics related to science, technology, society and the environment, the Science and Astronomy Clubs promote the development of projects on these topics, in addition to other scientific issues, considering that they are not isolated from the social, environmental, economic and political context. In 2019, considering the productions of the four Science and Astronomy Clubs referred to in session 3, we had the involvement of approximately 135 teachers, who guided about 422 projects, with the approximate participation of 1519 students, on the most varied themes involving different areas of knowledge and, addressing a wide diversity of research questions, such as environmental, social, health and economics, science and technology, regional culture, history, entrepreneurship, among others. Figures 3 and 4 show scenes from the Scientific Exhibitions that took place in two of the co-executing schools.

Figure 3. Scientific fair at João Pilati school

Figure 4. Scientific fair at Elisa Tramontina school

The students expressed interest and involvement with the scientific fair, both for the social interaction among colleagues, school and family, and for the opportunity to present something that they developed and produced, resulting in success in carrying it out.

The testimony of the scholarship holder teacher of one of the co-executing schools summarizes one of the main achievements of the scientific fair, validating the above assumptions: *"my greatest professional accomplishment took place today. The students were all engaged, all in search of knowledge, presenting themselves for all the community. It was an unforgettable moment. I believe that this is education. Teachers very enthusiastic about the projects and in questioning the students to evaluate the projects. Students from other schools are coming to appreciate students' projects, making them feel valued for their studies. Ex-teachers and ex-alumni helping and valuing the presentation of projects by students"*.

Table 1 shows the 37 best projects from the Science and Technology Clubs of the co-executing schools, approved to participate in MOSTRASEG. In Table 1, the name of the projects for each school is separated by semicolon. These projects were developed by a total of 63 girls and 26 boys.

Table 1. Best Projects from co-executing schools.

School	Projects
Tancredo de Almeida Neves	MoveT, a universe of possibilities.
Melvin Jones	Automotive Protection; Medicinal Plants: a study through the construction of a website; Piezoelectricity: piezoelectric uses; Pets: application development aimed at the residents of Caxias do Sul; Totalitarian Governments; Rare diseases: concepts and Brazilian legislation; Depression of adolescents in the XXI century; Science Club: a possible space; The influence of art on the development of mentally challenged children
João Pilati	Plastics and microplastics; The use of chatbots based on Artificial Intelligence for information; Vaccination: Problem or solution?; Weight sensor; Guide for the visually impaired; Biodegradable plastic.
Elisa Tramontina	Study for the development of organic paint to reduce environmental impacts and reuse of food; Study on the use of technologies in the school environment and their integration with current teaching methodologies; Study of alternative replacement of industrial glue components by tree sap for greater safety and resistance; Who are they?; Study of the use of hovenia dulcis as a way of analyzing the impact of exotic plants on our environment; Study of the replacement of paraffin present in candles with vegetable wax and cooking oil; The study of the influence of sound waves on the development of plants; Alternative treatment for wastewater from the washing machine and its relationship with fluid mathematics (phase II); Study of a method of producing a pencil from the vane; Carlos Barbosa in a matter of welcoming exchange students; Incorporation of manihot esculenta peel in the manufacture of incenses that are less aggressive to the environment and its role in the health of Indian women; Study of a method of creating a winch to reposition of dead people; Art gift study: research on the concept of thinking associated with the right and left brain; Medicine alarm clock: an alternative to help organize medicines for the elderly; Depression: 21st century science; Study of the feasibility of extracting cannabidioids from ruta graveolens for possible control of Parkinson's tremors; Use of araucaria angustifolia seed husks as a composite in wood agglomerates and MDF panels; Feasibility study of the use of peanut shell in the production of wood substitute panels; Use of lauric acid to fight acne.
Farroupilha	Learning deficit of high school students in Portuguese and Mathematics

4.2 MOSTRASEG

MOSTRASEG is an annual scientific and technological regional fair for students in 9th through 12th grades from cities close to Caxias do Sul, where is located the University main campus. At MOSTRASEG, students have a chance to show others their projects about their own scientific investigations and compete against the young scientists from other schools. To participate in MOSTRASEG, the research projects developed by the students are selected from their school's science fairs. The team project is formed by no more than three students who are guided by their teachers.

In September of 2019, the 11th MOSTRASEG occurred, and it was the biggest edition to date with 150 projects and more than 350 students from 26 schools. The female participation was 60% of total and 65% of the projects had one girl in the team at least.

Each project at MOSTRASEG are assessed by two researchers of UCS, and at least one of the evaluators works on the same field of the project. The evaluators receive the projects one week before the fair starts for a previous assessment. Then, in the two days of fair, the evaluators walk by the exhibition court and interview the project team for the final assessment. MOSTRASEG is a free event and all community is welcomed.

Figure 5 and 6 show the fair court with the students presenting their research projects.

Figures 5 and 6. Images of MOSTRASEG.

4.3 Co-executing schools' projects that received a prize at MOSTRASEG

The projects awarded in MOSTRASEG, by students from co-executing schools, are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Projects that received a prize at MOSTRASEG.

Prize	Project	School
Sustainability, Renewable energy and environment	Study of the use of <i>hovenia dulcis</i> as a way of analyzing the impact of exotic plants on our environment	Elisa Tramontina
Digital Technologies	The use of chatbots based on Artificial Intelligence for information	João Pilati
2nd place Elementary School	Guide for the visually impaired	João Pilati
3rd place High School	Incorporation of <i>manihot esculenta</i> peel in the manufacture of incenses that are less aggressive to the environment and its role in the health of Indian women	Elisa Tramontina
1st place High School	Study of the feasibility of extracting cannabidioids from <i>ruta graveolens</i> for possible control of Parkinson's tremors	Elisa Tramontina

4.4 Working with the feedback

After MOSTRASEG ended, a week later, an evaluation meeting of the projects that were developed in science clubs by scholarship holder students from co-executing schools was held at UCS. This activity was conducted by instructors of the EM&CT team with the aim of discussing and clarifying the items in the MOSTRASEG evaluation form, and to encourage self-assessment of the work, as a way of reflecting on aspects of improvement of new research projects to be carried out. in school science clubs.

At the first moment of this meeting, the scholarship girls from each school, accompanied by the scholarship holder teachers, got to know the MOSTRASEG evaluation form, discussed and recorded their doubts and understandings of the aspects that were evaluated. One by one, the following items were highlighted and proposed to be examined: field notebook, bibliographic binder, work exhibition panel, oral presentation, research relevance, applicability, application of scientific methodology and research report; exactly as they appear in the evaluation form used by UCS instructors who constitute the group of project evaluators.

The second moment was an exchange of ideas among all participants in the meeting. The scholarship girls reported what they understood about the evaluation items and presented questions to clarify their doubts. The scholarship holder teachers also participated, collaborating with explanations and inquiring about points that were unclear. The discussions were mediated by the instructors of the EM&CT team, who expanded and deepened clarifications for the doubts presented.

Then, as a third step, a self-assessment was proposed: the scholarship girls analyzed their own project and assigned a score from zero to ten for each item, as shown in the evaluation form, and wrote a brief opinion as a justification. for the assigned score.

In the fourth moment and final activity of the meeting, the scholarship girls reviewed their materials (field notebooks, panel photos, bibliographic binder and research report) seeking to analyze, identify and share aspects to be improved in their records, aiming at the next editions of MOSTRASEG.

Still, regarding this activity of evaluating the projects developed and presented by the scholarship girls at MOSTRASEG, we highlight its importance due to the active participation strategy adopted for its development. In addition, as it was promoted after MOSTRASEG, this activity allowed the girls to reflect on what they experienced in the entire process of developing and presenting their projects. With that, and with the interactions promoted, they were able to assign meaning to the aspects evaluated in their projects. Finally, the girls identified that they could improve their performances, as EMC&T fellows and while acting in the Science and Astronomy Clubs of their schools, suggesting that they can become science researchers.

5 Final Remarks

One of the guiding principles for the creation of science clubs is research as the process that, integrated into the school's daily routine, guarantees the suitable appropriation of reality, as well as projects possibilities for intervention. It combines the social character with the protagonism of the researchers (FREIRE, 1980), making them critical and reflective. With this same view, Demo (2000) justifies that, when going through the research process, the student has the opportunity to develop critical thinking, exercise reflection, becoming producer of knowledge and not just a transfer of information, in fact, with regard to research as a pedagogical principle, we highlight that: [...] research promotes the development of scientific attitude, which means contributing, among other aspects, for the development of conditions to interpret, analyze, criticize, reflect, reject closed ideas throughout life, learn, seek solutions and propose alternatives, enhanced by investigation and for the ethical responsibility assumed in the face of political, social, cultural and economic issues. [...] a conception of scientific investigation that motivates and guides action projects, aiming at improving the community and the common good (KÜLLER, 2011).

In this context, the EM&CT project structured this proposal that seeks to overcome the fragmentation of programs and actions, aiming at the creation of science clubs, as spaces for carrying out research and projects. All of this, taking place in a school where young people develop a culture through protagonism in transformative activities, with the possibility of exploring their vocational interests or professional options, their

perspectives on life and social organization, thus exercising their autonomy in formulating and rehearsing the realization of their life and society projects (KÜLLER, 2011).

As for the contribution of the study developed and presented here to the practice of basic education teachers/educational practitioners, it is worth pointing that all these activities were developed with five teachers in the Continuing Education Course, already mentioned, whose main objective has been to involve teachers from the co-executing schools as the main ones involved in the continuity of the actions that are being promoted in the project. In addition to the continuity of actions, it is intended that these teachers are multipliers of the ideas and actions that have been promoted with other students and with other teachers and managers of their schools. The course has been developed in line with the offer of the project's activities, but expanding the discussion on the theoretical aspects that underlie them, considering scientific, technological and pedagogical knowledge. Other editions of this course are being scheduled to assist teachers/educational practitioners from other schools in the region.

With activities like this, the school can, in addition to teaching, exercise the role of encouraging 21st century participation, teamwork, proactivity, creativity, collaboration and communication skills.

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